

Condition Monitoring of Industrial Elevators Based on Machine Learning Models

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Abstract—With the increasing demands for safe, robust and high efficient systems, the performance indicators should be quantified over the system’s life-cycle. Condition monitoring drastically reduce the maintenance costs, prevents unscheduled working interruption of the system, keeps productivity performance and the system in safe operating mode. Artificial intelligence and machine learning models are able to process big data sets, harness the data and predict the failures. This paper presents a method to monitor the states conditions and to identify the faults that may appear during the operation of an industrial elevator by developing a Long Short-Term Memory model.

Index Terms—Condition Monitoring, Machine Learning, Deep Learning, Elevator, Long Short-Term Memory

I. INTRODUCTION

Condition monitoring and fault diagnosis have been intensively studied in both academia and industry in the last decades. Once implemented, the maintenance costs are drastically reduced, the system unscheduled working interruption are prevented, and the productivity performance is kept at a high level [1]. Besides these aspects, the most important advantage of condition monitoring is that the system operates in safe conditions. Early detection of incipient faults leads to avoiding the harmful and devastating consequences of faults and failures.

Considering than more than 12 million lifts operate daily all over the world and that their numbers and use are increasing rapidly, a daily maintenance would require half a million hours of manual labour with a failure rate of over 164,000 times per day [2]. At the same time, the faults that appear during elevator operation result in increased costs. Therefore, in order to avoid them and keep the system safe and reliable, frequently examination is needed [3]. In

this context, various works have focused on the topic of condition monitoring. In [4], a remote condition monitoring approach of two elevator parameters, vibration and acoustics, using an Internet of Things device for remote data acquisition and remote fault indication is presented. The development of a cost-effective wireless sensor node for remote elevator condition monitoring and the engineering challenges faced during its implementations are described in [2], whereas in [5], a monitoring and warning system that uses camera, smoke alarm system is used to monitor the unsafe behaviours of passengers in the elevator.

Such methods require to develop a digital twin that allows to monitor the machine performance, predict the failures and perform system maintenance. Besides that, machine learning and artificial intelligence algorithms are needed to process big data sets gathered from the production lines [6].

This paper presents a method to monitor the condition state and to identify the faults that may appear during the operation of an industrial elevator. The aim is to characterise the operation mode of the system and to identify the faulty operation conditions. In this context, two possible faults are taken into account for this study, the rope sliding on the sheave and the sheave ageing. An individual machine learning model is developed for each fault and afterwards are connected to identify the two faults that may occur. The data needed to build the fault identification model is achieved by conducting dynamic simulations on a high fidelity parametric elevator model under different operation conditions. Afterwards, the resulting data is harnessed using machine learning algorithms, creating a machine learning model able to identify faults during the elevator operation.

The paper is structured as follows: a description of the

elevator system under study is identified in Section II. Section III presents the process of modeling the elevator faults within a dynamic simulation environment, together with a mathematical description of the faulty cases. The development of the machine learning model able to identify the system's faults is discussed in Section IV. Here, an evaluation of the prediction and fitting capabilities of the developed machine learning model is performed. Finally, Section V presents the conclusions.

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

An electro-mechanical elevator is driven by a motor that actuates the sheave-rope transmission to move the passenger cabin. In order to reduce the developed motor torque, the weight of the cabin and the passengers is partially balanced by introducing the counterweight. In this case, the electrical motor is represented by a permanent magnet synchronous electrical motor connected to the electronic unit, mainly represented by the inverter. Besides this, the elevator includes the cabin composed by a fixed mass that represents the frame and the variable mass to take into consideration the different load inside the cabin, cables, the control system that accurately controls the position of the elevator. As the elevator moves, the cables will experience a change in length, and, therefore, variable stiffness, elasticity and damping that modify as function of the length of the cable. Moreover, the model of the cables have a variable mass to take into account viscous friction.

Based on the description of the physical system, a virtual representation is created within Simcenter Amesim. Here, the functional relationship between the system's components, analytically represented, is performed. The graphical representation of the model developed in Simcenter Amesim can be identified in Fig. 1, whereas the main parameters of the system can be identified in Table I [7].

The control of the elevator is assured by a repetitive control strategy based system [7] that maximizes the elevator speed without sacrificing passengers comfort. Moreover, this type of control allows to compensate the disturbances caused by the motor torque ripple, pulleys, bearings and rail guides and deal with the system non-linearities (e.g., variation of the rope mass, variation of the rope stiffness as a function of position). The motor speed imposed by the controller unit can be identified in Fig. 2 a). For the situation when the load inside the cabin is null, meaning that the load lifted by the elevator is given only by the weight of the cabin frame, we can identify the negative electromagnetic torque from Fig. 2 b), as the movement of the cabin is due to the counterweight descent. Therefore, based on the imposed motor speed and simulation conditions, the cabin will move with the trajectory described in 2 c) at a velocity of maximum 1 [m/s], as displayed in 2 d).

III. SYSTEM FAULTS DESCRIPTION

A. Rope Sliding Modeling

The first fault that is studied and taken into account for condition monitoring is the case when the rope is shifting on

TABLE I
PARAMETERS OF THE ELEVATOR UNDER STUDY

Parameter	unit	value
Cabin mass	kg	600
Counterweight mass	kg	1650
Sheave Radius	m	0.5
Gear ratio	-	1/10
Cabin Viscous Friction	N/m/s	1
Sheave Viscous Friction	Nm/rad/s	15
Rope Young's Module	N/m ²	2.1 10 ⁹
Maximum reachable height	m	75

Fig. 1. Elevator schematic representation.

Fig. 2. Elevator results for load 0 case a) Imposed motor speed, b) Simulated electromagnetic torque, c) Cabin position and d) Cabin velocity.

Fig. 3. Sheave and rope.

the sheave. In this situation, a change of the friction coefficient between the cabin and the rope occurs. The schematic representation of the rope sliding phenomena can be identified in Fig. 3, where the rope is represented with blue line and the sheave is represented by the black circle. When the rope is sliding on the sheave, the movement of the rope is decoupled from the rotational movement of the sheave, as the dry friction force between the rope and sheave is changed. Therefore, a new variable is introduced, tangential rope velocity, denoted as v_{rt} . This value is directly affected by a modification of the coefficient of dry friction, and indicates whether the rope is considered as ideally stuck to the sheave, or whether it can slide. In the same figure, the purple dashed line represents the dry friction between the rope and the sheave.

The capstan equation [8] is used to compute the equivalent tangential force between the rope and the sheave with the following relation:

$$F_{\text{rope}} = F_{\text{resistance}} e^{\mu\beta} \quad (1)$$

$$F_{\text{resistance}} = \min(|F_{\text{end}_1}|, |F_{\text{end}_2}|) \quad (2)$$

where μ represents the coefficient of friction, β the wrap angle and $F_{\text{resistance}}$ is the smallest value of the rope forces at both sides of the rope that is wrapped around the sheave.

In order to model this effect in Simcenter Amesim, the coefficient of friction was varied in the developed high fidelity parameterised elevator model from 1 (ideal case) to 0.1. Five simulations scenarios were created by modifying the nominal load available in the cabin from 0% to 100% with a step of 25%. The first case, 0% nominal load available in the cabin, simulates the case when the elevator is empty, without passengers, and travels between floors, taking into consideration only the mass of the cabin and the mass of the counterweight. On the contrary, the fifth case is defined by the situation when the cabin is fully loaded, when the maximum mass of passengers permitted is on board. In this situation, the mass of the load, mass of the cabin frame and the mass of the counterweight are taken into consideration.

When the rope sliding phenomenon occurs, the cable is totally or partially decoupled from the sheave and the control unit is not able to properly manage the position of the cabin and to assure the comfort and performance targets. Moreover, the cabin will have a trajectory defined by the ratio between the the counterweight mass and its own load.

B. Sheave Degradation Modeling

For the second fault under study, the sheave aging was the main subject of the analysis. For that, it was considered that in time, the sheave loses its capabilities, affecting its efficiency and its outer diameter due to wear and tear. The friction between the sheave and the ropes, together with external factors, such as a corrosive medium or humidity, cause a reduction of the sheave diameter. At the same time, the degradation is affecting the torque characteristics. The efficiency (e) of the sheave applied to the torque depends on the acting mode of the torque with respect to the velocity, ω , (either braking or accelerating):

$$\begin{aligned} T &= T_{\text{sheave}} e, \text{ when } (T\omega < 0) \\ T &= T_{\text{sheave}} / e, \text{ when } (T\omega > 0) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

In order to assure a continuous operating mode, the transition between the two acting modes is obtained by using a hyperbolic function.

The data necessary to build the machine learning model that is able to identify this type of fault is obtained by running a set of simulations of the elevator model in Simcenter Amesim. Here, the efficiency of the sheave was varied from 1 (ideal case) to 0.1, with a step of 0.1. At the same time, the diameter of the sheave was reduced with up to 14% from the nominal value, with a step of 1.25% from the nominal condition. The generation of the designs of experiments was conducted using a full-factorial procedure. Like in the previous fault modeling, five simulations scenarios were created by modifying the nominal load available in the cabin from 0% to 100% with a step of 25%. The first case, 0% nominal load available in the cabin, corresponds to the empty cabin situation, whereas, the fifth case is defined by the situation when the cabin is fully loaded, when the maximum mass of passengers permitted is on board.

IV. FAULTS IDENTIFICATION

A. Machine Learning Model

After the simulation data is obtained for each fault, the obtained system responses is harnessed. A proper machine learning method is selected based on the obtained data sets (i.e., time-series waveforms). In this paper, two Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) are used to develop the faults identification model. The two LSTM networks are connected to learn the long-term dependencies of data in the multivariate time series input. The diagram of the model is in Fig. 4.

The training stages can be synthesized by the following methodology:

- 1) Load the time series dataframes for each variable.
- 2) Compute 160 samples, where every sample is the i -th column from each dataframe.
- 3) Standardize samples using sklearn's StandardScaler.
- 4) Load samples into pytorch Dataset.
- 5) Random split the samples, 60% for training, 20% for validation and 20% for testing.

Fig. 4. Neural network structure.

- 6) Train the model using a batch-size equal to 96 for training and 32 for validating.
- 7) Evaluate classification metrics on the test dataset.

Regarding the machine learning model configurations, for the second LSTM network, the last hidden state of the previous is used as input. A dropout layer is added between each LSTM layer to avoid overfitting. The output of the last LSTM network gets passed on to a linear layer, ending in an output layer through SoftMax activation function that should classify the input.

The identification of the elevator faults using machine learning models can be reduced to a classification problem. For this purpose, based on the extracted data sets, three classes that describe the elevator functionality were created:

- Class1 : Non-faulty.
- Class2 : Sheave is pulling on the rope.
- Class3 : Ageing of the sheaves.

Afterwards, each input was labeled as belonging to one specific case. The provided data set consists of 160 multivariate time series samples. Each sample contains six variables (inputs): state of the elevator brake (i.e., on/off), cabin acceleration, cabin position, cabin velocity, motor speed and motor torque, with 70000 time steps.

After the labels for each entry are computed, the data can be standardized. Standardizing is a common scaling approach that converts the probability distribution for an input variable to a standard Gaussian by subtracting the mean from the values and dividing them by the standard deviation. This way, the gradient descent algorithms used in for this study (i.e., Adam) converge faster when the features provided are on a similar scale.

In this scope, the standardization procedure was performed using Sklearn's StandardScaler [9], where every sample x is:

$$z = \frac{x - u}{s} \quad (4)$$

where u is the mean of the training samples and s is the standard deviation of the training samples.

The next step, the data set is divided into training, validation and test samples. The samples are randomly split in 60% for training, 20% for validation and 20% for testing. Dealing with a small dataset with only 160 entries, we can set the batch

Fig. 5. Training Time.

size of the training and validation data set to be equal to the number of samples, respectively 96 and 32. The training time is shorter, see Fig. 5 because only one back propagation is performed for every training epoch. Moreover, because the described classification problem has more than one class, an Adam optimization function [10], with Cross Entropy loss function, was used for the training process.

B. Results

The model accuracy, F1 Score and validation/training loss obtained for 200 epochs can be seen in Fig. 6. The spikes that can be identified in the evaluation metrics are mainly caused by the nature of the stochastic gradient descent algorithm and epochs, where a large number of neurons are ignored in the model because of the dropout layer.

The standard hyperparameter sampler is TPESampler, which applies the Tree-structured Parzen Estimator algorithm [11]. The objective function is firstly applied to the hyperparameter values that have been randomly selected from the supplied domain in the algorithm. The findings are divided into two groups after a number of observations depending on whether they fall inside or outside of a specific quantile of the observed values of the objective function. The best hyperparameter values can be distinguished from the others using the following process: in each iteration, the two groups are updated and a Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) is fitted to each group, producing two densities, $l(x)$ for the best hyperparameter values and $g(x)$ for the other ones, where x is the hyperparameter's value. Afterwards, the algorithm will select the value that maximizes the ratio between the two densities (i.e., $l(x)/g(x)$). For the case under study, 500 trials with the objective to maximize both the accuracy and the F1 Score on the testing dataset was considered. The hyperparameters optimized and their domains can be seen in Table II and Table III.

For the best combination of hyperparameters, the model achieved 96.75% accuracy and 0.96 F1 score on the testing dataset, as it can be identified in Fig. 7).

TABLE II
HYPERPARAMETERS AND DOMAINS.

Hyperparameter	Domain
LSTM layers	[1,9]
Learning rate	$[1 e^{-1}, e^{-5}]$
Dropout probability	[0,10,0.75]
Hidden size for LSTM networks	[32,512]

TABLE III
BEST HYPERPARAMETERS.

Hyperparameter	Best value
LSTM layers	2
Learning rate	0.01
Dropout probability	0.20
Hidden size for LSTM networks	32

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented a method to monitor the condition state and to identify the faults that may appear during the operation of an industrial elevator. Two potential elevator faults were taken into account for this study, the rope sliding on the sheave and the sheave ageing. For each individual fault, a machine learning model based on Long Short-Term Memory Network was developed. Later, they were connected in order to identify the two faults that may occur. Dynamic simulations performed on the developed high accuracy parametric elevator model within Simcenter Amesim were conducted in order to obtain the machine learning model necessary data. In order to obtain the machine learning best combination of the hyperparameters, an optimization process, with the objective to maximise the accuracy and F1 score, was conducted. By analysing the accuracy, F1 Score and validation/training loss of the optimized model, it has been demonstrated that the machine learning model is able to predict the faults with accuracy of 96.75%.

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Fig. 6. LSTM developed model metrics: (a) Loss, (b) accuracy, (c) F1 Score (d) and confusion matrix over the testing dataset.

Fig. 7. Trials and values based on accuracy and F1 Score.

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